

DISTRIBUTED PROCESSING SYSTEMS
SECURITY: COMMUNICATIONS, COMPUTER,
OR BOTH

Paul Woodie

National Computer Security Center
9800 Savage Road, Fort Meade, MD 20755
(301) 859-6044

ABSTRACT

Information security involves many components, including communication security, computer security, physical security, and personnel security. This paper deals only with communication and computer security. In systems that involve either communications systems or monolithic computer systems (but not both) the overall requirements for information security are relatively straightforward, or at least relatively well understood. However, in distributed processing systems that usually involve both communications and computer components, there is a need for both communications as well as computer security techniques. This paper addresses communications security, computer security, and their relationship in information protection in the distributed processing environment.

DISCLAIMER

The views contained in this paper are those of the author. This paper does not necessarily represent official policy of the National Computer Security Center.

INTRODUCTION

The protection of information so that it does not fall into the wrong hands or so that it is not in some way damaged or otherwise made unusable, is a subject of growing concern. Some aspects of this problem have been studied for years, and there have been a number of protection schemes and measures proposed (and used). Some of the more common of these protection measures are related to physical, personnel, tempest, communications, and computer security techniques. The technologies of the first three (i.e., physical, personnel, and tempest) are relatively well understood. The technology of communications security is also relatively well understood and has been applied for years to communications problems. Computer security technology, on the other hand, has been seriously studied for only the last ten or twenty years and is certainly neither well understood nor universally applied to solving today's information protection problems. Indeed, some of the information protection problems that we are experiencing today did not even exist ten or twenty years ago. For example, the widespread use of the "personal computer" is a relatively recent phenomenon. With that mass popularization of computing technology has come a large increase in

the number of "hackers," and the proliferation of threats to data stored in computers. To be sure, there have always been individuals who were intent on stealing information or otherwise causing havoc, but they were in the past relatively few in number.

This paper addresses the problems of information protection in distributed computer systems, and how communications security techniques and computer security techniques can be effectively combined to address these problems. The objective of this paper is to describe in general terms, data communications security issues, computer security issues, and the relationship between these two technologies, especially in the context of a distributed processing system.

In the early days of computer systems, computers generally were designed to function as "stand alone" processors of primarily numerical data. Later, isolated and stand-alone functions of payroll, records, etc. functions were added. Indeed, the idea of "batch processing" connoted an independent, physically and temporally isolated processing function. Protection of the information during this time period was relatively straightforward, and physical and personnel protection means usually provided a sufficient degree of security.

However, as the need for connection of computers into networks with communications grew, and the ideas of "distributed processing" grew, so did the need for information protection in the less-well-defined distributed processing environment. Indeed, the vulnerabilities of this information to undesirable effects has also increased, both due to the number of systems, and to the potential number of threats mentioned earlier.

The next section of this paper addresses communication security and computer security separately and will provide some of the background for considering how these two technologies can be effectively combined in distributed processing systems.

BACKGROUND

When either communications security or computer security is discussed, there are usually three facets of the problem that are addressed in some form: 1) Compromise protection; 2) Integrity protection; and 3) protection against loss or

denial of service (sometimes this is called "assured service"). It has been argued by some that the third facet, protection against denial of service, is not really a security issue but a performance or reliability issue. Nevertheless, it is considered here since it is usually addressed in some form when information security is addressed.

The degree of emphasis placed on each of these three security components is, more often than not, based on the perception of the threat in the particular organization. Within the Department of Defense, for example, the need for protection is most often associated with the need to guard "classified" or "sensitive" information. There are well established policies dealing with this area as it relates to computer systems (viz., DoD Directive 5200.28, Security Requirements for Automatic Data Processing Systems). This policy deals directly with the need, and the requirements, to protect information from compromise; that is, from allowing the information to fall into the wrong hands. Indeed, protection against compromise is designed to keep the information being protected from being disclosed to any party or other entity that has not been previously authorized to receive that information.

Integrity protection, on the other hand, is designed not to keep information from the wrong hands, but to ensure that information is not modified in any way by parties or other entities that have not been previously authorized to do so. The concern here is not keeping information hidden, but in ensuring that the information is always correct, and not modified or contaminated in some way. For example, if I wanted to provide compromise protection to the amount in my bank account, I would not let you see my bank book. If I was interested in providing integrity protection, I would (perhaps) let you see my bank book, but I would not give it to you so that you could change the amount shown in it. Hence, I could be sure that, although both you and I know the amount, no one has changed the amount, and thus it is correct.

Continuity of service, sometimes referred to as prevention of "denial of service," is sometimes considered an information security issue. Depending on the specific security policy involved, and to some extent on the specific threat perceived, it may or may not be an explicitly stated requirement. In any case, it is usually an implicit requirement of any system. Availability of service, whether for a communications system or a computer system, is usually considered something desirable. It should be noted that the denial of service referred to here is the reduction of the availability of service to some arbitrarily low level by some means outside the control of the system. For example, if I can arbitrarily make it impossible for you to communicate, or just reduce the level of service below that guaranteed or specified, then I have effectively denied communication service to you. One can make a strong case, in some circumstances, that denial of service is a legitimate security concern. For example, if a burglar cuts your telephone line before he comes into your house to rob you, he has denied (to you)

telephone service just when you need it most. That certainly is a security concern, at least at that moment.

In summary then, there are three main types of protection that could be considered under the heading of information protection: compromise protection, integrity protection, and denial-of-service protection. Compromise protection is probably the most common means of information protection considered, integrity protection the next most common means considered, and denial of service protection the least common means of information protection considered. However, the order provided here may vary substantially depending on the specific requirements and the organization involved.

The reason for providing protection is to overcome the (sometimes) hostile threats that would serve to defeat our system. A passive threat is defined as an unintended leakage or receipt of information; i.e., an incident where an entity does not change the information but only receives it. Telephone wiretapping for the purposes of monitoring is an example of this. An active threat, on the other hand, actively inserts itself into the information transmission process so that the information that is received by the legitimate receiver is not what was sent by the sender. An example would be a wiretap that changed my telephone dialer so that I always got the wrong number. (In this case, the threat also created a denial-of-service problem for me!)

COMMUNICATIONS SECURITY ISSUES

Communications security has been studied and employed for many years. For example, ancient kings used "signet rings" and wax seals to secure messages against disclosure. In more modern times, there have been code wheels and cipher cylinders, used primarily in war time, but really any time that privacy of communications was desired. These techniques have given way to electronic encryption methods in this electronic era. The primary motivation for this technology in the past has been privacy of information (our compromise protection model), but there are also integrity benefits which can be derived.

The commonly used cyclic redundancy code is one example of such an integrity-preserving use of encryption techniques. Another would be the use of enciphering of the plaintext of the message to produce an n-bit code at the end of the message (called a Message Authenticating Code (MAC) in Federal Information Processing Standard (FIPS) 81) which is appended to the plaintext message and is used in a manner similar to the CRC as a check of the message integrity or authenticity.

In the case of the CRC, the algorithm and "key" is publicly known so that anyone could have either prepared the message at the sending end or determined the message integrity at the receiving end. In the case of the MAC, using secret keys, only parties possessing the key could produce the

MAC on the sending end and correctly determine the message integrity at the receiving end. In addition, since the key is presumed secret, and the encryption algorithm sufficiently strong, it can be assumed that only a party possessing the key could have sent the message. This, in essence, is message authentication.

A convenient example of the above technology and its application in data communication systems is the Data Encryption Standard and the various implementations of it in the data communications environment. Federal Information Processing Standard (FIPS) 46 <1¶ describes the data encryption algorithm, and FIPS 81 <2¶ describes how this algorithm can be applied to data communications systems, in terms of encryption modes of operation. While FIPS 46 describes how the individual bits are manipulated to produce the encrypted output, FIPS 81 describes the various modes that this mechanism could be used in and the relative merits of these modes for different applications. Federal Standard 1026, describes how the DES algorithm in FIPS 46, when used in one of the modes of operation described in FIPS 81, can be integrated into a standard data communications system at the physical level of the International Standards Organization Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) communications architecture. This allows encryption techniques to be applied in computer communications systems at the most basic level, the physical level (sometimes called level 1, the so-called RS-232c level).

As long as data communications lines are strictly point-to-point, encryption works well. However, as communications circuits become combined into common user switched networks, the limitations of encryption at level one become more pronounced. The reason is that information encrypted at level one must be decrypted (to become plaintext) at every switching point in order for the address and other control information to be usable by the communications switches. This raises switching costs (by requiring more secure or reliable switching machines and more reliable and trustworthy operations personnel) and also the risk of compromise or other damage to the data being protected. Encryption at the higher levels of the OSI architecture eliminates some of these disadvantages. For example, if data is encrypted at level 3, then the addressing and control information necessary at the intermediate switching points can be used without the need for decrypting at those intermediate points. The encryption/decryption pair is needed ONLY at the information origination and destination points (hence the term, end-to-end encryption).

COMPUTER SECURITY ISSUES

Unlike communication security, computer security has been seriously studied for only the last ten or twenty years. Even so, this field has stabilized enough that a more or less standard definition of security could be developed. This standard which has emerged represents the first major effort of this type, and surely will be

followed by similar computer-related standards such as computer network standards, office automation standards, etc. Actually, this standard, the Trusted Computer System Evaluation Criteria, August 1983 (TCSEC83) <3¶, was developed as a result of the research efforts of the Department of Defense, and reflects the security policies of that particular body. However, these policies are not sufficiently unique that they are not applicable to other fields of endeavor. Indeed, it has been forcefully argued by some <4¶ that the TCSEC83 is broad enough to be used by DoD, civil government, and commercial organizations. What follows below is a brief explanation of the TCSEC83, including the broad objectives of the standard, the requirements, and some of the implications for distributed systems.

First, we need some basic concepts. Subjects and objects are two concepts used in trusted computer systems. A subject is an active entity, generally in the form of a person, process, or device that causes information to flow among objects or changes the system state. Technically, it is a process/domain pair. An object is a passive entity that contains or receives information. Access to an object potentially implies access to the information it contains. Examples of objects are: records, blocks, pages, segments, files, directories, directory trees, and programs, as well as bits, bytes, words, fields, processors, video displays, keyboards, clocks, printers, network nodes, etc.

There are three basic requirements, each consisting of two parts, from which the computer security requirements in TCSEC83 derive:

- o Security Policy,
- o Accountability,
- o Assurance

Security Policy

The first requirement associated with security policy is that there must be an explicit and well-defined security policy enforced by the system. In other words, before we can design a "secure computer system" we must know what the computer system is expected to do, what it is expected to do to provide security.

The second requirement, also associated with security policy, is that after we know what the system is supposed to do, how it is to protect data, there must be some way that data to be protected is identified.

Accountability

The third requirement, associated with accountability, concerns user identification. Individual subjects must be identified. Access control or other security policy must be based on who is accessing the information and what classes of information they are authorized to deal with. This identification and authorization information

must be securely maintained by the computer system and be associated with every active element that performs some security-relevant action in the system.

The fourth requirement, for audit, is also related to accountability. The collection of audit information is necessary so that, should a compromise or other security-related incident occur, there is a method to trace back and determine what happened. Good audit information enables us to determine: 1) who did it, 2) how extensive is the problem, and 3) what was compromised.

Assurance

The fifth requirement is related to assurance. The computer system must contain hardware/software mechanisms that can be independently evaluated to provide sufficient assurance that the system enforces the requirements stated above. The point here is that the computer system must be able to protect its internal mechanisms from any tampering that would inhibit its ability to enforce security.

The sixth requirement is that the trusted mechanisms that enforce these basic requirements must be continuously protected against tampering and/or unauthorized changes. A system that is determined to be secure today must be maintained just as secure tomorrow if it to be trusted.

There are 27 different specific requirements in the TCSEC83 that are derived from these six basic requirements stated above. These requirements are summarized in Figure 1. They have been grouped into four basic groups on the chart: Security Policy, Accountability, Assurance, and Documentation. Actually, these 27 types of requirements can be thought of as representing only two basic types of parameters: 1) security-related features (e.g., access control) and 2) assurances that those features work correctly and have not become defective through poor design, implementation, or subsequent modification or tampering. For example, if I have a computer system that is supposed to enforce a policy that I can only use the system between 9 a.m. and 5 p.m., but by some clever manipulation I can set the system clock to 10 a.m. any time I desire, then I can get around the access control FEATURE because the system protects itself poorly, or, stated another way, has poor ASSURANCES that it works as it is supposed to. The security FEATURES of the system tend to be those attributes of the system that are most user-visible whereas the ASSURANCES tend to be those things that are least user-visible (but perhaps most important).

The TCSEC83 uses the term "Trusted Computing Base" to describe the system that enforces the computer security requirements described above. A "Trusted Computing Base" is the totality of protection mechanisms within a computer system -- including hardware, firmware, software, and, in some cases the operator -- the combination of which is responsible for enforcing a security policy. This concept will be very important to us later as

we discuss how comsec and compusec measures can be combined in automated processing systems.

Actually TSEC83 was written to translate DoD computer security requirements for general purpose, multi-user computer systems. It was written in such a way as to be general in nature and applicable to many different systems, each with its own peculiar type of implementation (e.g., word size, memory allocation scheme, etc.). The general computer system model used was a single, stand-alone system. I will choose to call this type of system a monolithic system. Hence, the TCSEC83 most easily addresses monolithic computer systems. However, the TCSEC83 is also general enough that it can be applied to other types of automated processing systems. For example, consider the case of a monolithic, conventional bus-oriented computer system, where components such as processors, memory, and I/O devices are connected through a common information bus.

This information bus is the communications channel through which the various computer components communicate. Because of its relatively small size, and close physical proximity, and (assumed) correct design, it is assumed (i.e., trusted) not to 1) send information to the wrong component, 2) corrupt the information or introduce errors, and 3) to be available to the components of the system when it is needed. In fact, this information bus is expected (trusted) to satisfy the three security properties discussed above: compromise, integrity, and denial of service protection.

In the systems above, all the components are coupled closely enough, many times they are in the same cabinet, that they form one entity, and hence the term 'monolithic.'

However, if we were able somehow to physically lengthen the bus through some type of communication mechanism but still maintain the close coupling between the components, we would then have a 'distributed' system that still had the same essential characteristics as the 'monolithic' system discussed earlier. What matters here is not the physical proximity of the components but the 'logical' proximity. In both the monolithic and distributed system, the components are relatively tightly coupled to each other. The components are not autonomous; they work together as a single entity, albeit physically separated. A distinctly different case is a network, where the components are (perhaps) physically separated AND logically autonomous. Even here, the TCSEC83 is general enough that it addresses the general characteristics needed for security.

The final type of automated processing system that I would like to address here is the 'embedded' system; i.e., a computer system that is inside some larger system and is programmed to perform some function that, by itself, is not primarily user-visible, but rather is a part of some larger system. An example would be a(n otherwise) general purpose system that is inside a spacecraft and is programmed to perform only orbital calculations.

The traditional security concerns of compromise, integrity, and denial-of-service protection are important (in varying degrees) but the system is not user-visible and manipulable in the same sense that a large system with many user terminals is. Even here, the TCSEC83 is useful in that it describes some of the overall system security concerns that should be considered. For example, the 'object reuse' requirement states that information from one user should not accidentally be available to a subsequent user. In our embedded system, we should ensure that orbital parameters from one orbit are not left laying around in some unused memory space so that they are accidentally used in the calculation of a subsequent orbit.

Thus, the TCSEC83, although most easily adaptable to monolithic, multiuser computer systems, is also useful for distributed systems, networked systems, and embedded systems. In the monolithic system case, it can be applied directly. In the distributed case, it can also be applied directly if the various components of the distributed system are tightly coupled through trustworthy communications channels. In the case of a networked system, the concepts of the TCSEC83 can be used, but they must be interpreted in the context of the overall system. The same is true of an embedded system. One must ask what the system is expected (and trusted) to do, and use the requirements in the TCSEC83 accordingly.

COMSEC AND COMPUSEC PROTECTION MODELS

Now that we have introduced some basic concepts of communications security and computer security, let us examine how the two are related. We will first examine a "byword" that could be associated with communication security and another for computer security. The byword for communication security is "ISOLATION," while the one for computer security is "CONTROLLED SHARING." The primary protection technique used for communication security is encryption, the transformation of a set of data, using some (usually known) algorithm and some (usually private) key or seed, into another set of unintelligible data. The only intended way of recovering the data is through use of the same key and algorithm to do a reverse transformation of the data. The overall objective is to 'isolate' the data from all but the intended recipient. Sharing the data among a number of users is possible only through the mechanism of giving each user the (same) 'key' that can decipher the data. It can be assumed (at least for the purposes of this discussion) that all encryption algorithms and keys provide the same degree of security, and hence that all information is equally protected. Another way of stating this is that the only way to receive data is through the use of the receiving 'key' and there is no mechanism, other than giving away the key, of sharing information. Another implication of this is that all information is of equal sensitivity or importance, since it is accorded equal protection.

The byword for computer security, on the other hand, is "controlled sharing." In the TCSEC83 the

emphasis is on sharing of information in a controlled manner as opposed to strict isolation of information. For example, the Discretionary Access Control (DAC) requirement (which is a "feature" requirement) in the TCSEC83 describes mechanisms to specifically allow sharing of information (within the prescribed limits of DoD security policy). While it is true that, especially at the higher levels of the TCSEC83, the default is no sharing (complete isolation), yet the focus of the described features are policies and mechanisms for sharing in a controlled manner.

From the two bywords, and the concepts behind them, we can derive some general principles that can aid us in applying both comsec and compusec techniques to computer systems. Three cases will be considered: 1) monolithic systems, 2) distributed systems, and 3) networked systems. In the case of monolithic systems, all of the components of the TCB (e.g., processors, memory, and I/O) are in a single integrated environment such as a single cabinet with perfect, error- and interference-free communication between the components. Stated another way, there are no passive or active threats to the communication among the components of the TCB in a monolithic computer system. This is the most straightforward application of the TCSEC83. Another characteristic of a monolithic computer system is that there is tight coupling between all the components of the system such that only together can they be considered a complete TCB. Hence, inside the TCB there is relatively little need for communication security techniques. Of course, the need for communication security on communications lines (e.g., remote terminals, inter-mainframe links, etc.) still exists, and in fact, cannot be replaced by computer security techniques.

A distributed system is a rather small departure from the monolithic system, at least as far as the requirements of the TCSEC83 are concerned. In the distributed system, the same components of the TCB are present, and are closely coupled to each other. The major difference is that these components are now physically (or logically) separated from each other and connected through imperfect, error- and interference-prone communication channels. Stated in communications security parlance, these channels are subject to passive and/or active threats. If we can remove, or otherwise eliminate the results of these communication threats, we can consider the distributed system TCB to be equivalent to the monolithic system TCB. It is here that comsec techniques are most useful. They can be used to effectively restore the error-free communications channels that were present in the monolithic computer system TCB. In fact, there are no effective computer security measures that can replace communication security for the interconnection of components in the distributed TCB.

A network, on the other hand, represents a rather large departure from the monolithic and distributed case. In a network, we typically have components that are independent computer systems by

themselves (e.g., hosts) which are not tightly coupled as in the case of monolithic systems, but loosely coupled. They are also usually physically separated by error- and interference-prone communications channels. In addition, especially in some packet networks, the communications channels may be slow and have unpredictable transit delays. Hence, there is the need for independent, security-related processing to be done at these host locations, and any security-related information that is communicated over the network communication channels can be assumed to have been subject to passive and/or active communication threats. Stated another way, we have independent TCBs connected through untrusted communications channels. Here there is a clear need for communications security techniques to protect the communication channels. In fact, no amount of computer security techniques alone can replace the need for communications security on the communications portion of this network.

Actually, networks can be viewed from at least two different perspectives, and the resultant application of standards depends to some extent on the view taken. The first view is that the composite of ALL the independent TCBs WITH the communications channels connecting them should be viewed as a single entity for the purposes of information protection. The communication channels that exist should be protected with whatever means is necessary to ensure error- and interference-free communications. Each of the (host) components of the network should be trusted, and there is a close enough coupling between the components that the network can be viewed as a complete, unified entity.

The proponents of this view would state that the same security requirements that are applied to monolithic systems can be applied to an entire network. True, there would need to be some amount of interpretation of the TCSEC83, but in principle is applicable as it stands. For example, one of the requirements in the TCSEC83 is for auditing so that an audit trail of security-related events can be maintained. Proponents of this 'integrated' view of networks may hold that as long as this function is accomplished SOMEWHERE in the network, the intent of the requirement is satisfied without the letter being satisfied at each and every node/host.

There are others that feel that the necessity to 'interpret' the TCSEC83 to a network context is an invitation to water down computer security requirements. This view states that each component of the network should be an independent TCB which can enforce security in and of its own right. The network, if it contains computers, should also have a separate security criteria which can be applied to it, specifically tailored to communications-oriented computer systems (which, in fact, is what a network such as ARPANET is). However, whether a network is viewed from either perspective, there is a clear necessity to apply communications security techniques to the communications part of the network.

Regardless of which view of networks is taken, it is apparent that distributed processing is becoming more prevalent. As technology makes the means more readily available through improved digital communications systems and less expensive and more widely available computing facilities, there will be more and more distributed processing systems, whether of the distributed or the network variety. Indeed, this author maintains that the major company business trends toward centralization and now to decentralization are in part results of the tools that technology is making available.

SUMMARY

As we have seen, information security traditionally has been seen as encompassing three different protection requirements: 1) compromise, 2) integrity, and 3) denial-of-service. These requirements, in varying degrees, exist (either explicitly or implicitly) in all systems. Communications security technology has been studied and applied for many years whereas computer security technology is relatively young and is still developing at a much more rapid pace than communications security technology. However, the two technologies are merging. For example, AT&T, traditionally a communications company, is now becoming a computing company as well. IBM, traditionally a computing company, is now branching out into communications as well. Hence, from both a business and technology perspective, the two technologies of communications and computing are merging (and indeed in some cases, becoming indistinguishable). The principles mentioned above (i.e., physical proximity, logical proximity, and the degree of coupling of components) can form a valuable framework from which to evaluate not just computer security or communications security but rather 'information security.'

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TRUSTED COMPUTER SYSTEM EVALUATION CRITERIA SUMMARY CHART

Figure 1